

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN THE MODERN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM: REGGIO EMILIA APPROACH

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Abstract. This article analyzes the best international practices used in the modern preschool education system, specifically the theoretical foundations and practical implications of the Reggio Emilia approach. The article highlights the role of this approach in the development of a child's personality, its impact on the development of creativity, independent thinking, and communication skills. It also highlights the key principles of the Reggio Emilia method—viewing the child as the central subject, the role of the environment in education, and collaboration between parents and educators. The possibilities of integrating this approach into the national preschool education system are also discussed.

Keywords: preschool education, Reggio Emilia approach, international experience, child development, creativity, educational environment, pedagogical collaboration, innovative methods, student-centered education, education system.

Introduction

In recent years, the reform of the preschool education system in our country has been carried out at a rapid pace. Improving the quality of education in this area, adapting it to world standards, and using international experience have become urgent tasks of the day. Uzbekistan is using a number of advanced international experiences in preschool education.

In order to assess the quality of education in Uzbekistan, a system for monitoring the quality of preschool education and assessing child development indicators has been introduced in cooperation with UNICEF.

In some regions of Uzbekistan, the MELQO (Measuring Early Learning Quality and Outcomes) education quality assessment system developed by UNICEF is used. This assessment methodology serves to assess the level of readiness of preschool children for school education and the results of the quality of education.

The Montessori methodology focuses on independent learning and individual development of children. This methodology has been widely used in preschool education for many years.

STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) is intended to develop logical thinking and problem-solving skills in children. This technology is also used in modern preschool educational organizations in our country.

Now the Reggio Emilia approach is entering the preschool education system of Uzbekistan. We will find answers to the questions: what is the Reggio Emilia methodology, what does it give to the child, and what are its advantages?

Methodology

The Reggio Emilia Methodology is a child-centered early childhood education philosophy that focuses on developing creativity and independent thinking. The Reggio Emilia approach

originated in Reggio Emilia, Italy, after World War II and has been widely adopted in the United States, Sweden, Australia, the United Kingdom, and Asia since the 1980s. Its founder is the Italian teacher and psychologist Loris Malaguzzi (1920-1994). He is known worldwide as the first founder of the Reggio Emilia style of early childhood education. [1]

He also emphasized the importance of mutual respect, open communication, creativity, and experiential learning in children's development. Reggio pedagogy was formed on the basis of these principles, and the approach to education became famous for its child-centeredness. International interest in Reggio pedagogy has grown since the 1987 annual National Conference on Early Childhood Education, which has continued to grow. Today, the Reggio Emilia approach has been adopted by more than 145 countries. [4]

The Reggio Emilia approach is a widely used pedagogy in preschool education worldwide, and its results are significantly different from those achieved by traditional pedagogy.

Loris Malaguzzi advocated the recognition of children as individuals with rights and potential, their active participation in the learning process, and the development of creative expression. He emphasizes inquiry-based learning in an aesthetically rich environment, in partnership with parents. This approach is internationally recognized for its ability to foster creativity, critical thinking, and community participation in early childhood education.

According to this approach, democratic education involves the interaction of educators, families, and the social environment in educating children. In this way, education should be carried out in a community-based, collaborative manner, rather than in an isolated setting.

Malaguzzi's Reggio Emilia approach is based on the idea that children play actively in the learning process, express their ideas through various forms of communication, while expressing confidence in the child's potential, and supporting him through various means. [3] The methodology is a modern approach that approaches the child as an individual, recognizing and helping to realize his creativity and, at the same time, his innate abilities. According to the approach, the teacher is required not only to be a teacher, but also to be a guide, listener, observer and partner of the child. Educators should value each form of expression of children, take into account their interests, and organize education on the basis of projects.

The Reggio Emilia approach sees the child as an active, creative, and independent thinker in education. In this, the child does not receive knowledge ready-made, but rather acquires it by discovering it for himself. In the approach, the child's environment is considered a "third teacher" in his own experience. This emphasis on the environment in the Reggio Emilia approach is similar to the support for experiential learning of John Dewey, one of the founders of American pedagogical design. [2]

Discussion

In Reggio pedagogy, the child's environment is a creator of learning opportunities. Its proponents argue that children learn more through simple objects than through "special" toys. The methodology suggests that in a pedagogical environment, unusual materials such as clay, stone, sand, wood, metal particles, fabric, threads, parana feathers, various types of paper and cardboard, tree branches, tree bark, various dry plants, their seeds, nuts, shells and other materials can be the necessary tools for children to create. Natural elements such as wood, stone or shells can initiate sensory exploration in a child. Instead of relying on ready-made toys, educators are encouraged to use unusual materials that encourage children to create their own

discoveries. Ordinary objects can become any desired object in the child's imagination. Educators need to support and follow these same interests of children.

The group room should be organized in an open, bright space equipped with natural materials, visual displays of the educational process. Art studios, ateliers are symbolically represented for practical experiments, and separate areas are allocated for them. The most important aspect of Reggio pedagogy is that materials for learning should be independently and freely chosen by children. These materials can be searched for together with children from the accumulated reserves or from nature outside. Ideas that arise even in a small corner of the group room can become a place of discovery that develops over time.

The following principles are followed in organizing a creative and practical environment in Reggio pedagogy:

1. Aesthetic principle. The environment should be visually beautiful, have color harmony and consistency. Use light, mirrors, natural materials.
2. Open flexibility. Certain corners (art, construction, experiment, sensory) are changed depending on the interests of children. Materials are kept open for children's free activity.
3. Learning through experience. Children experiment with materials of their choice: clay, sand, water, paint, light, etc.
4. Collaboration and socialization. Large tables and open spaces are necessary for group work. Many activities are based on dialogue, discussion, and collaborative problem-solving. [4]

The organized environment is the starting point for the child to find answers to his questions. Teachers should not immediately answer children's questions, but rather allow them to search for answers to these questions through experiments with them. For example, children learn how to create colors from natural materials themselves and dye threads. This is a very interesting experience for them. For this, natural materials from the prepared reserve, such as tree bark and dried flowers, can be used.

The result of the work done is not limited to words, but also reinforced through their own actions, stories, and drawings. Telling a story about the work done serves to reveal ideas in a broad sense. You can even move on to the process of staging it in an art center. This allows the child to study the issue they are studying from different perspectives.

Participation in joint activities is very important in the educational process. Educators need to be partners with children, asking questions that encourage them to think, and creating an environment where children feel more confident and their ideas are valued, rather than acting as instructors.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the application of the Reggio Emilia approach in the preschool education system requires the creation of a flexible educational environment suitable for the development of the child. Such an approach serves the socialization of the child, the free expression of his own thoughts, independence and the formation of life skills. Therefore, the application of Reggio Emilia pedagogy in preschool education is not only an enrichment of the curriculum, but also the formation of an educational culture that respects the personality of each child, revealing his individual aspects. As we continue to study innovative approaches to education, the principles of this methodology provide valuable insights into the upbringing of the minds of early childhood children and the formation of their independence in the current changing times. Currently, interest in the Reggio Emilia approach is growing as part of the modernization

of the preschool education system in our republic. Direct scientific research is being carried out on this approach in Uzbekistan. Preschool education specialists are conducting extensive methodological research to integrate international experiences, including the Reggio Emilia approach, into the "First Step" state curriculum.

When implementing it in Uzbekistan, it is not necessary to copy it completely, but to adapt it to the requirements of our region and apply some of its elements. Of course, such adaptations require in-depth scientific research from researchers in the field of education.

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